

Joint research project 2023-2025
of National Research Council (IT) & Romanian Academy (RO)

Comparison of CNOSSOS-EU and NMPB methods for road noise modelling in Italy and in Romania

Aims

TO COMPARE NMPB AND CNOSSOS-EU IN TEST AREAS IN TUSCANY AND BUCHAREST

TO TEST 3 DIFFERENT INPUT DATA COLLECTION APPROACHES FOR ROAD TRAFFIC FLOWS

TO EVALUATE NOISINESS OF LIGHT VEHICLES AND COMPARE WITH RESULTS OF NOISE MODELS

TO INVESTIGATE ON CNOSSOS-EU RELIABILITY AS A FUNCTION OF INPUTS, ESTABLISHING THE DATA COLLECTION METHOD ACCURACY

TO HELP IN DECISION MAKING AND NOISE CONTROL PROCESS TO SPARING MONEY WHILE ACHIEVING SUFFICIENT ACCURACY.

TO ENHANCE CAPACITIES IN BOTH INSTITUTIONS, PERFORMING VISITS AND SHARING EXPERIENCES.

Tested input acquisition methods

NOISE MAPPING

How to collect traffic counts when road traffic database are not available?

Figure B.1. Location of equivalent point sources on light vehicles (category 2), heavy vehicles (categories 3 and 4) and two-wheeler (category 4)

AI-based low-cost cameras

Standard microwave traffic counter

Traffic models based on Google API travel times

Methods are tested with this setup: TC and CAM are attached to a pole together with noise measurement station.

Innovative input data collection: CAM

Features:

	Camera	Low cost
	Case Camera	Dome → high distortion
	Processing Unit	Raspberry Pi
	Supply	Battery powered
	Energy use	5W

Classification according to CNOSSOS-EU categories:

Category	Name
1	Light motor vehicles
2	Medium heavy vehicles
3	Heavy vehicles
4	Mopeds and motorcycles

At the end of the transit, the following information is calculated:

- **ID:** vehicle identification number
 - **Vehicle class**
 - **Detection accuracy**
 - **Vehicle position with temporal distance** (speed and acceleration derived)
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- A new system is under development
 - The actual version is able to calculate lively the number of passages for CNOSSOS vehicles categories and directions

Fiorella et al. “Challenges in real-time low-cost vehicle recognition systems for CNOSSOS-EU input”, Forum Acusticum EURONOISE, Malaga (ES), 23-26 June 2025

Innovative input data collection: API

- A complete pipeline in Python which is able to transform travel times (provided by Google API) into noise levels at receivers
- This include an attenuation matrix obtained in a commercial software

- Traffic model allow to infer flows from travel time when the flow is stable
- Modal split must be derived by local data
- Technique has been tested in PRIN OUTFIT Project, developing a method to derive dynamic flow data. <https://sites.google.com/view/prin2022outfit/home>
- With the help of commercial software an environmental- static abatement matrix is derived.
- Then noise estimate is derived summing up together the sound power level of the source (dynamic) + Propagation (static)

Tested scenarios:

April -September 2024

Instrumented roads (24h)

	Road	Lanes	Speed (km/h)	Distance from buildings (m)
1.	Regional road, SR439, Massarosa,	IT-Rg	50	10-10
2.	Residential street, Secuilor St., Bucharest	RO-Re	30	15-20
3.	Boulevard, C-tin. Brancoveanu Blvd.	RO-Bd	50	25-25

Vehicles/hour (day/evening/night)

1. ~ 600/400/100

2. ~ 500/300/60

3. ~ 1300/1000/300

- Italy: a low noise surface aged 6 years on a regional road in small village context

- Romania: two roads in Bucharest, sector 4, Berceni.

CNOSSOS & NMPB

- Measurements allowed to compare models with CNOSSOS-EU and NMPB starting from the same inputs.
- Differences with measurements vary on data collection methods because modal split matters, but NMPB resulted higher than measurements of at least 2.6 dB.
- Differences between CNOSSOS and NMPB ranges from -7,6 to -2,6 dB according to place, timeslice and input method.

- Measurements also allow comparison of single light vehicle noisiness in Italy and in Romania and their comparability is confirmed.
- Thus, 1 car in CNOSSOS is noisy as 0,6 cars in NMPB approximately

- As a consequence, when comparing NMPB interim maps with new ones with CNOSSOS-EU, and the old were not well calibrated, the new ones might be about 2.2 dB less in terms of hourly Levels without a change in flows (and neither a change of real noise levels exposure) only due to light car calibration.

NMPB 96

At least
-2,2 dB

Common
Noise Assessment Methods
in Europe (CNOSSOS-EU)

Summary of input data collection results

- In Italy and in Romania TC has been installed in different positions, resulting in different possible inaccuracy in the identification of vehicles categories.
- Traffic flow estimated with CAM are generally 5% higher than TC ones.
- API works quite well on daytime and on boulevard since a minimum traffic is needed to derive flows from Google travel time.

Total vehicles estimated by each method in each scenario are reported:

Narrow time intervals, dynamic mapping capabilities

- Dynamic noise mapping can help in dealing with short term issues as rush hour, school entrance/exit routing management
- Accuracy of traffic estimates in narrow intervals has been studied comparing estimated levels against measured ones.

Mean difference (dB(A))	1 - Regional, IT			2 -Residential, RO			3 -Boulevard, RO		
	TC	CAM	API	TC	CAM	API	TC	CAM	API
day	-1.7	-3.4	-2.5	-2.1	-0.7	-0.4	0.5	1.0	2.1
evening	-1,8	-2.7		-1,8	0.1	0.1	0.9	1.4	1.7
night	-2,8	-3.8		-1.9	0.0	-5.4	3.3	3.8	1.5
overall	-2.1	-3.4		-1,9	-0.3	-2.4	1.7	2.2	1.8

- Masking of vehicles might influence both noise levels and traffic counting with TC and CAM, leading to maximum differences in estimated levels when the traffic is enough to mask a correct counting but not enough to absorb noise.
- Generally low traffic flows (evening, night) are well mapped with TC and CAM, while API is not suitable. On the other hand, well tuned API system is much reliable when counting masking effects occur.

Maximum absolute difference (dB(A))	1 - Regional, IT			2 -Residential, RO			3 -Boulevard, RO		
	TC	CAM	API	TC	CAM	API	TC	CAM	API
day	3.3	5.0	5.6	5.6	3.5	3.7	4.6	2.8	3.8
evening	2.4	3.4		4.2	3.1	2.9	5.8	3.4	2.8
night	5.7	7.9		13.0	11.3	11.7	8.2	3.5	5.2
overall	5.7	7.9		13.0	11.3	11.7	8.2	10.8	5.2

SWOT analysis

	Helpful	Harmful
Internal	Strengths Easy installation; Day/night same accuracy; Fast installation and simple equipment.	Weaknesses Might underestimate flows in case of congestions; Categories need local setup; Cannot be controlled remotely.
External	Opportunities Commercial product.	Threads Can be damaged.

TC

	Helpful	Harmful
Internal	Strengths Optimal identification of vehicles; Can identify flow for each lane in the same direction.	Weaknesses Might overestimate flows in case of congestions; Live time systems are under development; Cannot be controlled remotely.
External	Opportunities Relatively cheap; Algorithms can be applied to standard surveillance cameras; Can be used to feed ITS systems.	Threads Can be damaged; Initial setup might require short road closing; Fog and rain might influence.

CAM

	Helpful	Harmful
Internal	Strengths Can be acquired remotely.	Weaknesses Doesn't work in case of low traffic flows; Needs modal split knowledge and post processing analysis; Available for selected roads.
External	Opportunities Can be used for a number of different applications and models (ITS, pollution models).	Threads Costs for API service.

API

Perspectives

- A preliminary visual check demonstrated that TC and CAM loose less than 10% in medium - low traffic roads and that CAM best performs in terms of categorization, while API might differ more than 30% when traffic is below 150 vehicles/h but further studies are needed for complete validation.

- The use of innovative input data collection methods can be further investigated and tested on large scale noise maps
- Enhanced systems for traffic data collection will be available for live time elaborations
- API services can be exploited to derive traffic flows for major roads and time representative of average flows such that maps can be derived without many on site surveys

- CNOSSOS-EU detailed input improve noise maps not only with higher accuracy when compared to measurements but also with higher precision compared to NMPB when varying the input data collection method.

- Noise mapping includes also population exposure and health evaluations. This aspects are paramount but have not been included in this study. Further collaboration are envisaged to deep knowledge on health, disturbance and exposure estimates. A specific proposal have been submitted.

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